

Single Beacon-Based AUV Navigation: A Comparative Study of Kalman Filters

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Abstract—This paper compares the performance of two algorithms for the navigation of an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) based on a single hydroacoustic beacon. The performance of two algorithms, the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF), is evaluated through numerical simulations in various scenarios to determine their accuracy in estimating the AUV's position using velocity and range measurements. The results of this study provide insights into the strengths and limitations of these two algorithms in the context of AUV navigation.

Index Terms—navigation, single beacon, UKF, EKF

I. INTRODUCTION

The localization of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) during underwater navigation poses a significant challenge, and has been widely investigated in recent years. The challenge is due to the lack of GPS signal available in the underwater environment, because of the high attenuation that electromagnetic waves suffer in seawater and, in the absence of specific positioning systems, can exclusively rely on dead-reconing techniques [1]. To overcome this, various acoustic-based positioning systems have been developed, such as Long Base Line (LBL), Short Base Line (SBL) and Ultra-Short Base Line (USBL) systems, which use the time of flight of acoustic signals to measure ranges to fixed transponders and determine the AUV's position via trilateration algorithms.

In LBL acoustic localization systems, the AUV measures the ranges to a set of transponders placed in fixed and known positions in the sea, and it estimates its position via trilateration algorithms. SBL systems do not require any seafloor mounted transponders or equipment and thus are suitable for tracking underwater targets from boats or ships. Three or more transducers mounted on a surface vessel request replies from a transponder installed on-board the AUV, and the AUV position is estimated via trilateration. In USBL systems, transceiver is mounted on a vessel and uses acoustic signals to determine the distance toward AUV. Transponder is attached to AUV, and it replies to acoustic signals from the transceiver with its own acoustic pulses, allowing the transceiver to calculate the AUVs position. While these

techniques have been widely used and have been successful in many applications, they are still prone to errors due to channel limitations, such as frequency dependent attenuation, Doppler spread and multipath propagation [2]. Therefore, these techniques are often usable only for relatively short periods, and the AUVs are often required to surface in order to acquire a positioning fix from the GPS.

In recent years, new techniques, such as the Range-Only and Single-Beacon methods tracking have been developed to enhance the performance of AUVs in more complex scenarios, offering a promising solution to the localization problem [3]. These approaches are based on the use of range measurements to a single node with the aim of developing simple, cheap and easy to operate solutions.

In general, ROSB methods are based on an autonomous vehicle which is used as a tracker. This vehicle periodically performs new range measurements using the Time Of Flight (TOF). TOF is the measurement of the time taken by an object, particle or wave to travel a distance in order to determine distance, speed or properties of the medium. In traditional single beacon underwater tracking, the time of arrival (TOA) is often measured at each acoustic receiver. Then, it is converted into the transit time based upon a known time of emission (TOE). Using this transit time with the knowledge of the effective sound velocity (ESV) yield the range measurement, as described in [4].

Some works have been performed in single beacon navigation [1], [3], [5], [6], [7] and in this paper comparative analysis of Kalman filters for single-beacon tracking will be presented. We will carry numerical simulations and show that UKF is generally more stable and has faster convergence rate, while EKF is superior in a specific initialization case, which will be analyzed in section 4.

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 problem definition is stated and model of the AUV is presented; in Section 3 we review Extended Kalman Filter and Unscented Kalman Filter; in Section 4 we present the simulations in tabular and graphical form and discuss the results; in Section 5 we summarize the conclusions and briefly outline future work.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

To simplify the notation and the problem, we assume that AUV moves in a 2D plane. However, this assumption can be relaxed if vehicle can measure its own depth. Furthermore, we assume that the vehicle is fully actuated and can be

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modeled as double integrator with the acceleration as a control input

$$\begin{cases} \dot{p} = v, \\ \dot{v} = u + \omega, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $p \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the AUV position, $v \in \mathbb{R}^2$ it the AUV velocity, while $w \in \mathbb{R}^2$ represents the disturbance signal/process noise.

The vehicle computes its own control input every Δt units of time. If we denote $t = k\Delta t$, then (1) can be expressed in discretized form as [3]

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k + \omega_k \quad (2)$$

where

$$x_k = \begin{bmatrix} p_k \\ v_k \end{bmatrix}, A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2}\Delta t \\ \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

whereas ω_k represents discrete process noise that we assume to be Gaussian with covariance matrix Q .

The measurement vector $y_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ of the vehicle can be written as

$$y_k = h(x_k) + \nu_k \quad (4)$$

where ν_k is a zero-mean Gaussian noise with covariance matrix R . Furthermore, the measurement function is defined as

$$h(x_k) = \begin{bmatrix} \|q_k - p_k\| \\ v_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

This means that the vehicle can measure velocity v_k via the Doppler Velocity Log (DVL) and the range to the beacon by means of the acoustic modem and range-measuring devices. The range between the AUV and the beacon is defined as

$$\|q - p_k\| = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_{k,1})^2 + (q_2 - p_{k,2})^2}. \quad (6)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the fixed beacon position that is known to the AUV.

The problem we analyze in this paper consists of estimating the vehicle's position and velocity based on the range and DVL measurements.

III. SINGLE-BEACON NAVIGATION FILTERS

A. Extended Kalman Filter

Extended Kalman Filter [8] [9] is the nonlinear extension of the Kalman filter which linearizes the system dynamics and measurement function about the current state estimate. There are two phases in EKF - prediction and correction.

In the prediction step, EKF predicts the states and the covariance matrix based on the discretized AUV model (3)

$$x_k^- = Ax_{k-1}^+ + Bu_{k-1}, \quad (7)$$

$$P_k^- = AP_{k-1}^+ A^T + Q. \quad (8)$$

In the correction step, the Kalman gain is calculated as

$$K_k = P_k^- C_k^T (C_k P_k^- C_k^T + R)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

while the states and covariance matrix are updated after collecting a new measurement

$$x_k^+ = x_k^- + K_k (y_k - h(x_k^-)) \quad (10)$$

$$P_k^+ = (I - K_k C_k) P_k^-. \quad (11)$$

At each time step the Jacobian matrix of $h(x_k)$ is computed as

$$C_k = \left. \frac{\partial h(x_k)}{\partial x} \right|_{x_k^-} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(q_1 - x_{k,1}^-)}{\sqrt{(q_1 - x_{k,1}^-)^2 + (q_2 - x_{k,2}^-)^2}} & \frac{(q_1 - x_{k,1}^-)}{\sqrt{(q_1 - x_{k,1}^-)^2 + (q_2 - x_{k,2}^-)^2}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Since the state dynamics is linear, the matrix A does not need to be updated.

EKF pseudocode is given by Algorithm 1. Note that in this implementation, the correction step is not executed at each time instant. Typically range measurements are obtained every 1s, while Δt can be adopted to the smaller value.

Algorithm 1 EKF Algorithm for Single-Beacon Navigation

Input: $\Delta t, y_k$, new range

Output: target state estimation \hat{x}_k^+

if Init **then**

Initialize: $A, B, R, Q, P_0^+, \hat{x}_0^+$

end if

Predict step:

$\hat{x}_k^- = A\hat{x}_{k-1}^+ + Bu_{k-1}$

$P_k^- = AP_{k-1}^+ A^T + Q$

if New range **then**

Update step:

$C_k = \left. \frac{\partial h(x_k)}{\partial x} \right|_{x_k^-}$

$K_k = P_k^- C_k^T (C_k P_k^- C_k^T + R)^{-1}$

$\hat{x}_k^+ = \hat{x}_k^- + K_k (y_k - h(\hat{x}_k^-))$

$P_k^+ = (I - K_k C_k) P_k^-$

end if

B. Unscented Kalman Filter

The Unscented Kalman Filter [10] is a derivative-free algorithm that addresses the approximation issues of the EKF as well as requirement for noises to be Gaussian. UKF addresses these issues by utilizing a deterministic sampling strategy where a set of points, called sigma points, are propagated through the true nonlinearity without approximation. The unscented transformation is used to calculate the statistics of a random variable which undergoes a nonlinear transformation. This method completely captures the true mean and covariance of the probability distribution, and when propagated through the true nonlinear system, captures the posterior mean and covariance accurately to the 3rd order for any nonlinearity. Various methods can be used to choose the sigma points. In this case, the method presented in [11] has been used, where

$$\chi = [\hat{x} \quad \hat{x} + \gamma\sqrt{P} \quad \hat{x} - \gamma\sqrt{P}] \quad (13)$$

where $\gamma = \sqrt{n + \lambda}$, with $\lambda = \alpha^2(n + k) - n$. λ is a scaling parameter. α determines the spread of the sigma points around \hat{x} and is usually set to a small positive value

(e.g. 10^{-3}). k is a secondary scaling parameter which is usually set to 0 and β is used to incorporate prior knowledge of the distribution of x (for Gaussian distributions, $\beta = 2$ is optimal).

Finally, the sigma points are weighted as follows

$$W_0^{(x)} = \frac{\lambda}{n + \lambda}, \quad (14)$$

$$W_0^{(P)} = \frac{\lambda}{n + \lambda} + 1 - \alpha^2 + \beta, \quad (15)$$

$$W_i^{(x)} = W_i^{(P)} = \frac{1}{2(n + \lambda)}, i \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}. \quad (16)$$

UKF implementation is given by Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 UKF Algorithm for Single-Beacon Navigation

Input: $\Delta t, z_i$, new range

Output: target state estimation \hat{x}_k^+

if Init **then**

 Initialize: $A, B, R, Q, P_0^+, \hat{x}_0^+$

end if

Predict step:

$$\chi_{k-1}^+ = [\hat{x}_{k-1}^+, \hat{x}_{k-1}^+ + \gamma\sqrt{P_{k-1}^+}, \hat{x}_{k-1}^+ - \gamma\sqrt{P_{k-1}^+}]$$

$$\chi_f = f(\chi_{k-1}^+, u_{k-1})$$

$$\hat{x}_k^- = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} W_i^{(x)} \chi_f$$

$$P_k^- = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} W_i^{(P)} [\chi_f - \hat{x}_k^-] [\chi_f - \hat{x}_k^-]^T + Q$$

if New range **then**

 Update step:

$$\chi_k^- = [\hat{x}_k^-, \hat{x}_k^- + \gamma\sqrt{P_k^-}, \hat{x}_k^- - \gamma\sqrt{P_k^-}]$$

$$\chi_h = h(\chi_k^-)$$

$$\hat{y}_k^- = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} W_i^{(x)} h_{\chi, i}$$

$$P_{\chi_h \hat{y}} = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} W_i^{(P)} [\chi_{h, i} - \hat{y}_k^-] [\chi_{h, i} - \hat{y}_k^-]^T + R$$

$$P_{\hat{x} \hat{y}} = \sum_{i=0}^{2n} W_i^{(P)} [\chi_i - \hat{x}_k] [\chi_{h, i} - \hat{y}_k^-]^T$$

$$K_k = P_{\hat{x} \hat{y}} P_{\chi_h \hat{y}}^{-1}$$

$$\hat{x}_k^+ = \hat{x}_k^- + K_k (y_k - \hat{y}_k^-)$$

$$P_k = P_k^- - K_k P_{\chi_h \hat{y}} K_k^T$$

end if

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to evaluate the performance of the EKF and UKF algorithms for AUV navigation, simulations were conducted using MATLAB. The AUV control law is defined as $u(t) = 4(v_r(t) - v(t))$, where $v_r(t) = \dot{p}_d(t) - 0.5(\hat{p}(t) - p_d(t))$. This control law ensures that the AUV follows the desired trajectory, which in this example is given by the Lemniscate of Bernoulli

$$p_d(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 50m \end{bmatrix} + 50m \begin{bmatrix} \cos(0.01 \text{rad/s} \times t + \frac{\pi}{2}) \\ \sin(2 \times 0.01 \text{rad/s} \times t + \pi) \end{bmatrix}.$$

The beacon is at position $q = [0 \ 0]^T$. The sampling time is set to $\Delta t = 0.1s$, while the range measurements are collected with a frequency of $0.5Hz$. The following values of the covariance matrices and initial conditions are set in both the EKF and UKF: $Q = 10^{-4}I$, $R = \text{diag}(10^{-3} \ 10^{-6} \ 10^{-6})$, $P = \text{diag}([30 \ 30 \ 0.1 \ 0.1])$. The approximate position of the AUV should generally be known, so knowing that, we can set state covariance matrix which represents the uncertainty of the estimated state of the system.

Fig. 1. AUV trajectories for initial positions $p_0 = [20, 10]$ (solid lines) and $p_0 = [-20, 10]$ (dash lines)

Fig. 2. Estimation error for initial positions $p_0 = [20, 10]$ (solid lines) and $p_0 = [-20, 10]$ (dash lines)

Fig. 3. Tracking error for initial positions $p_0 = [20, 10]$ (solid lines) and $p_0 = [-20, 10]$ (dash lines)

The simulated trajectories of the AUV with initial positions of $p_0 = [20, 10]^T$ and $p_0 = [-20, 10]^T$ are depicted in Figure 1. It showcases the effective performance of both algorithms when the AUV promptly finds and follows the desired path. The estimation error and tracking error are shown in Figures 2 and 3. It can be seen that EKF reaches steady state faster in the case where the AUV initial position is in the same quadrant as the filter initial state. On the other hand, EKF exhibits poor convergence when states are not properly initialized. The UKF performs similarly in both cases.

To further compare the filters performance, we introduce the following metrics:

- 1) $E_{t_0}^{t_f} = \frac{1}{t_f/\Delta t - t_0/\Delta t + 1} \sum_{k=t_0/\Delta t}^{t_f/\Delta t} (x_k - \hat{x}_k^+) (x_k - \hat{x}_k^+)^T$,
- 2) $T_{t_0}^{t_f} = \frac{1}{t_f/\Delta t - t_0/\Delta t + 1} \sum_{k=t_0/\Delta t}^{t_f/\Delta t} (x_k - p_d) (x_k - p_d)^T$.

It should be noted that $E_{t_0}^{t_f}$ represents the squared estimation error averaged on time interval $[t_0, t_f]$ sec, while T_{k_0} denotes the averaged squared position tracking error.

Table I shows the filters performance based on estimation and tracking error. Simulations were performed with a predefined fixed initial position p_0 , where $p_0 \in \{[5, 5]^T, [-5, 5]^T\}$,

TABLE I
FILTERS PERFORMANCE FOR FIXED INITIAL AUV POSITIONS

Metric	Filter	p_0^1	p_0^2	p_0^3	p_0^4	p_0^5
E_{1000}^{1500}	EKF	0.1561	0.1710	0.1670	0.1712	0.1594
	UKF	0.1465	0.1489	0.1546	0.1378	0.1474
E_0^{1500}	EKF	0.1516	2.3229	0.3136	45.8141	52.5812
	UKF	0.3780	0.3296	4.0314	4.2053	2.0214
T_{1000}^{1500}	EKF	0.1625	0.1775	0.1739	0.1782	0.1660
	UKF	0.1533	0.1557	0.1615	0.1444	0.1546
T_0^{1500}	EKF	1.8160	4.0052	2.1099	47.7566	56.1851
	UKF	1.8502	1.8013	5.1944	5.6208	7.1758

$[20, 10]^T$, $[-20, 10]^T$, $[-15, 10]^T$. Simulations were run 100 times for each position and results are averaged. Note that E_{1000}^{1500} indicates the filter performance in a steady state, while E_0^{1500} takes into account both the transient and steady state. The same holds for T_{1000}^{1500} and T_0^{1500} . From the Table I, it can be concluded that E_{1000}^{1500} and T_{1000}^{1500} are approximately equal for both UKF and EKF, but UKF has a slightly smaller value. When it comes to the results over the entire interval, the values depend on the predefined fixed position of the AUV, and it can be concluded that error using EKF is always smaller when the initial AUV position is initialized in the same quadrant as the initial filter state. In this case, EKF is more robust in terms of initialization error. In every other case, when the initial position of the AUV is outside of the quadrant of the initial filter state, UKF yields better results. This means that although EKF and UKF have similar steady state performance, UKF is generally more stable, whereas EKF is more sensitive to initialization. These results are in correlation with results shown in Figures 2 and 3.

TABLE II
FILTERS PERFORMANCE FOR RANDOM INITIAL AUV POSITIONS

Metric	Filter	r_0^1	r_0^2	r_0^3	r_0^4	r_0^5
E_{1000}^{1500}	EKF	0.1752	0.1683	0.1445	0.1759	0.1619
	UKF	0.1409	0.1388	0.1348	0.1448	0.1421
E_0^{1500}	EKF	1.8002	7.3283	18.7280	29.9595	60.1730
	UKF	0.2524	0.5730	1.1072	2.3785	4.1206
T_{1000}^{1500}	EKF	0.1822	0.1755	0.1511	0.1828	0.1683
	UKF	0.1476	0.1455	0.1414	0.1515	0.1489
T_0^{1500}	EKF	4.0144	9.6377	21.2583	32.5363	62.9999
	UKF	2.3450	2.6997	3.4820	4.7789	6.6670

As Table I, Table II shows the filters performance based on estimation and tracking error. The simulation is run 100 times as well, but with a different approach. In each iteration, a new random position of the AUV is set, where each position has the same distance (range) r to the coordinate origin. The following set of ranges is considered $\sqrt{p_{0,1}^2 + p_{0,2}^2} = r_0 \in \{5, 10, 15, 20, 25\}$. When it comes to results presented in Table II, the same can be concluded for E_{1000}^{1500} and T_{1000}^{1500} as in Table I. The findings also indicate that as the initialization error increases, both the estimation and tracking errors, represented by E_0^{1500} and T_0^{1500} , over the

entire interval become greater. Since the EKF is superior only when the AUV position is in the same quadrant as the initial filter state, it means that in this scenario, where numerous simulations are done and initial position of the AUV can be in any quadrant, UKF will always produce better results.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this paper indicate that Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) is more stable and less prone to initialization error when it comes to AUV navigation. However, there is a specific circumstance where EKF is consistently superior, and that is when AUV initial position and filter initial position are located in the same quadrant. In terms of steady-state performance, both filters produce similar results, but the EKF tends to have a slower convergence rate.

In future work, the plan is to investigate the issues surrounding EKF initialization and identify an optimal approach for initializing the filter. In addition, a more accurate AUV model will be considered.

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